

VIBRATION ANALYSIS OF IRREGULARLY SHAPED LAMINATED THICK COMPOSITE PLATES

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ABSTRACT

A simple but effective method of calculating the natural frequencies of vibration of some structural members with irregular shapes and mixed boundaries is presented herein. This method consists of determining the deflected mode shape of the member due to the inertia force under resonance condition. Beginning with initially "guessed" mode shape, "exact" mode shape is obtained by the process similar to iteration. The method of application of this method to the first mode vibration analysis of two dimensional problems including composite laminates was reported at JISSE 1. Extension of this method to the second mode vibration of such problems was reported at the Eighth Structures Congress of American Society of Civil Engineers in 1990. Present paper demonstrates that this method can be applied to the laminated thick composite plates with good accuracy. In general, "exact" result can be obtained after only three cycles. Numerical illustration is shown in detail and the results of some examples are given.

KEYWORDS : Vibration; Composites; Laminates; Thick Plates; Characterization.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials can be used economically and efficiently in broad civil engineering applications when standards and processes for analysis, design, fabrication, construction and quality control are established. Design and analysis of any structural member involves calculating influence coefficients, from which displacements, moments, and shears can be obtained, under all kinds of anticipated loadings. After materials and cross sections of each member are designed according to the result of such calculation, vibration and stability problems are analysed. In case of a laminated composite plate with boundary conditions other than Navier or Levy solution types, or with irregular cross section, analytical solution is very difficult to obtain. Numerical methods for

eigenvalue problems are also very much involved in seeking such a solution. According to Timoshenko(4), Friedrich Engesser offered a method for calculating critical buckling loads by successive approximation(1893). To get an approximate solution, he suggested the adoption of some shape for the deflection curve which satisfies the end conditions. This curve gives a bending-moment diagram, and the corresponding deflections can be calculated by using the area-moment method. Comparing this calculated deflection curve with the assumed one, an equation for determining the critical value of the load can be found. To get a better approximation the calculated curve is taken as a new approximation for that of the buckled bar and repeats the above calculation. An Italian engineer L.Vianello offered a graphical method in which the initially assumed curve could be given graphically, instead of taking an analytical expression, and the successive approximations could be made in graphical way. Lord Rayleigh in his famous book, The theory of sound(1877), offers method of obtaining an approximate value of frequencies of vibration of complicated systems by assuming a suitable form for the type of motion, thus transforming the problem to that of the vibration of a simple oscillator. A method of calculating the natural frequency corresponding to the first mode of vibration of beam and tower structures was developed and reported by the author in 1974. Recently, this method was extended to the first mode vibration analysis of two dimensional problems including composite laminates, and reported at the first Japan International Society for the Advancement of Materials and Process Engineering Symposium and Exhibition in 1989. Further extension of this method to the second mode vibration of such two dimensional problems was reported at the Eighth Structures Congress of American Society of Civil Engineers, 1990. This paper presents the result of further extension of this method to the vibration analysis of thick laminated composite plates. The effect of plate geometry and transverse shear deformation are presented. In order to illustrate this method, some details already reported by the author(1,2,3) are repeated in this paper.

2. METHOD OF ANALYSIS

A natural frequency of a structure is the frequency under which the deflected mode shape corresponding to this frequency begins to diverge under the resonance condition. From the deflection caused by the free vibration, the force required to make this deflection can be found, and from this force, resulting deflection can be obtained. Starting from an arbitrarily assumed mode shape, the force required for this mode shape can be found, and "new" mode shape corresponding to this force system is obtained. If the mode shape as determined by the series of this process is sufficiently accurate, then the relative deflections(maximum) of both the converged and the previous one should remain unchanged under the inertia force related with this natural frequency. Vibration of a structure is a harmonic motion and the amplitude may contain a part expressed by a trigonometric

function. Considering only the first mode as a start, the deflected shape of a structural member can be expressed as

$$w = W(x,y)F(t) = W(x,y)\sin\omega t \quad (1)$$

where

- W : the maximum amplitude
- ω : the circular frequency of vibration
- t : time

By Newton's Law, the dynamic force of the vibrating mass, m, is

$$F = m \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial t^2} \quad (2)$$

Substituting Equation(1) into this,

$$F = -m(\omega)^2 W \sin\omega t \quad (3)$$

In this expression, ω and W are unknowns,

In order to obtain the natural circular frequency, ω , the following process is taken. The magnitudes of the maximum deflection at a certain number of points are arbitrarily given as

$$w(i,j)(1) = W(i,j)(1) \quad (4)$$

where (i,j) denotes the point under consideration. This is absolutely arbitrary but educated guessing is good for accelerating convergence. The dynamic force corresponding to this(maximum) amplitude is

$$F(i,j)(1) = -m(i,j)[\omega(i,j)(1)]^2 w(i,j)(1) \quad (5)$$

The " new " deflection caused by this force is a function of F and can be expressed as

$$w(i,j)(2) = f\{m(i,j)[\omega(i,j)(1)]^2 w(i,j)(1)\} \\ = \sum_{k,l} \Delta(i,j,k,l) \{-m(i,j)[\omega(i,j)(1)]^2 \cdot w(i,j)(1)\} \quad (6)$$

where Δ is the deflection influence surface. The relative(maximum) deflections at each point under consideration of a structural member under resonance condition, $w(i,j)(1)$ and $w(i,j)(2)$, have to remain unchanged and the following condition has to be held.

$$w(i,j)(1)/w(i,j)(2) = 1 \quad (7)$$

From this equation, $\omega(i,j)(1)$ at each point of (i,j) can be obtained, but they are not equal in most cases. Since the natural frequency of a structural member has to be equal at all points of the member, i.e., $\omega(i,j)$ should be equal for all (i,j), this step is repeated until sufficient equal magnitude of $\omega(i,j)$ is obtained at all (i,j) points. However, in most cases, the difference between the maximum and the minimum values of $\omega(i,j)$ is sufficiently negligible for engineering purposes. The accuracy can be improved by simply taking the average of the maximum and the minimum, or by taking the value of $\omega(i,j)$ where the deflection is the maximum. For the second cycle, $w(i,j)(2)$ in

$$w(i,j)(3) = f\{m(i,j)[\omega(i,j)(2)]^2 w(i,j)(2)\} \quad (8)$$

the absolute numerics of $w(i,j)(2)$ can be used for convenience. In case of a structure

member with irregular section, including composite one, and non-uniformly distributed mass, regardless of the boundary conditions, it is convenient to consider the member as divided by finite number of elements(1). The accuracy of the result is proportional to the accuracy of the deflection calculation.

3. NUMERICAL ILLUSTRATION

3.1 Simply Supported Beam(1)

As an illustration of the presented method, a simply supported beam with uniform flexural rigidity, EI, is considered(1). The length of the beam is 10m. The weight of the beam is assumed as 500kg per meter. The weight acts as the mass when the beam vibrates and is treated as concentrated loads at five equally spaced points. Since a beam is one-dimensional, one subscript, i, is used. The initially guessed maximum amplitude, $W(i)(1)$, is assumed as follows.

$$W(1)(1) = W(5)(1) = 40$$

$$W(2)(1) = W(4)(1) = 80, W(3)(1) = 100$$

$$m(i) = 1 \text{ Mg/gram at all of } i.$$

These values are substituted into Equations(4) and (5), and from Equation(6), the following result is obtained.

$$w(1)(2) = 1616m(1)[\omega(1)(1)]^2 / EI$$

$$w(2)(2) = 4220m(2)[\omega(2)(1)]^2 / EI$$

$$w(3)(2) = 5216m(3)[\omega(3)(1)]^2 / EI$$

Letting $w(i)(1)/w(i)(2) = 1$,

$$\omega(1)(1) = 0.1573A(1), \omega(2)(1) = 0.1376A(2), \omega(3)(1) = 0.1385A(3),$$

where $A(i) = \gamma EI/m(i)$. Since all $\omega(i)(1)$ s should be equal at all of i points, this process has to be repeated. For the second cycle, only the relative magnitude of the amplitude is necessary, and $W(i)(2)$ s are assigned as follows.

$$W(1)(2) = W(5)(2) = 16.2, W(2)(2) = W(4)(2) = 42.2, W(3)(2) = 52.2$$

The same influence coefficient for the first cycle is repeatedly used, and the "new" amplitude, $w(i)(3)$, is obtained as

$$w(1)(3) = 827.76[\omega(1)(1)]^2 A(1)^2$$

$$w(2)(3) = 2167.08[\omega(2)(1)]^2 A(2)^2$$

$$w(3)(3) = 2678.64[\omega(3)(1)]^2 A(3)^2$$

From $w(i)(2) / w(i)(3) = 1$,

$$\omega(1)(2) = 0.1397A(1), \omega(2)(2) = 0.1396A(2), \omega(3)(2) = 0.1395A(3)$$

One more process is executed in order to obtain the better result as follows.

$$\omega(1)(3) = 0.139575A(1)$$

$$\omega(2)(3) = 0.139575A(2)$$

$$\omega(3)(3) = 0.139575A(3)$$

Note that all As are the same, thus $A = A(i)$, and $\omega = 0.139575A$.

The result obtained by the "exact" theory is $\omega = 0.139575A$. It is noted that the result of the first cycle is good enough for engineering purposes. If ω at the point of the maximum deflection, $\omega(3)(1)$, is considered, it is only 0.77% away from the "exact" result. In case of a variable cross section, $A(i) = E(i)I(i)/m(i)$ should be used. Influence coefficients can be found with relative ease at any case.

3.2 Simply Supported Antisymmetric Angle-Ply Laminated Plate

As an example, a square plate with the edge length $a = 1m$ is considered. The plate has $(30^\circ, -45^\circ, +45^\circ, -30^\circ)$ angle ply laminates and uniform mass, m .

Material properties are,

matrix elastic modulus $E_m = 3.8 \text{ Gpa}$
 fiber elastic modulus $E_f = 70 \text{ Gpa}$
 matrix poissons ratio $\nu_m = 0.35$
 fiber poissons ratio $\nu_f = 0.22$
 matrix volume ratio $V_m = 0.4$
 fiber volume ratio $V_f = 0.6$

Extensional stiffness, $A(I,J)$, bending extension coupling stiffness, $B(I,J)$, and bending stiffness, $D(I,J)$, are calculated.

The plate is divided by six equidistant lines at each edge. The 36 equal amount of mass, $1/6 \times 1/6 \times m$, are at the center of each segment.

For the first mode, the initially assumed mode shape is,

$$w(i,j) = \begin{vmatrix} 10 & 20 & 30 & 30 & 20 & 10 \\ 20 & 30 & 40 & 40 & 30 & 20 \\ 30 & 40 & 50 & 50 & 40 & 30 \\ 30 & 40 & 50 & 50 & 40 & 30 \\ 20 & 30 & 40 & 40 & 30 & 20 \\ 10 & 20 & 30 & 30 & 20 & 10 \end{vmatrix}$$

After calculating influence surfaces by laminate plate theory, the process similar to the previous example is taken, and the following result is obtained.

$$\begin{aligned} \omega(i,j)(2) &= (2393.9 \sim 2440.2)/\gamma m \\ \omega(i,j)(3) &= (2404.3 \sim 2406.8)/\gamma m \\ \omega(i,j)(4) &= (2404.8 \sim 2404.9)/\gamma m \end{aligned}$$

Result by Whitney is

$$\omega = 2404.81/\gamma m$$

For the second "mode", the initial mode shape is assumed as,

$$w(i,j) = \begin{vmatrix} 10 & 20 & 30 & 30 & 20 & 10 \\ 20 & 30 & 40 & 40 & 30 & 20 \\ 30 & 40 & 50 & 50 & 40 & 30 \\ -30 & -40 & -50 & -50 & -40 & -30 \\ -20 & -30 & -40 & -40 & -30 & -20 \\ -10 & -20 & -30 & -30 & -20 & -10 \end{vmatrix}$$

After taking the same steps as the first mode case, the following result is obtained.

$$\omega(i,j)(2) = (6798.7 \sim 7011.8)/\gamma m$$

$$\omega(i,j)(3) = (6830.8 \sim 6897.1)/\gamma m$$

$$\omega(i,j)(4) = (6844.1 \sim 6847.5)/\gamma m$$

The solution by Whitney is,

$$\omega = 6845.10/\gamma m$$

3.3 Simply Supported Symmetric Orthogonal Laminated Thick Plate

A rectangular plate with lengths of "a" and "b", and with the total thickness of the plate, t, is considered. The laminated plate has $[0^\circ, 90^\circ]$ s orientation. The material properties are as the previous example.

In order to study the effect of thickness on vibration properties, the values of (a/t) is given from 1 to 100. The effect of plate shape is studied by changing (a/b) from 1 to 5. For the influence surfaces, the solution by Whitney, for the thick plate deflection assuming the shape of the transverse shear in the form of a parabola, is used. This result is compared with the case of neglecting the transverse shear deformation. The later case is studied by simply using the Navier solution for the influence surfaces. The result is shown in FIGURES 1 and 2. FIGURE 1 shows the effect of the thickness of the plate on vibration characteristics. FIGURE 2 shows the effect of transverse shear deformation on vibration. The second mode case, which is not shown in the FIGURES has similiar characteristics. When a/t is 10, the first mode case is 12% different and the second mode case is 37% off. When a/t is 20, the first mode is 1% off and the second mode is 8% off. Plate aspect ratio a/b, when a/t is 100, influences vibration characteristics as follows.

a/b	1	2	3	4	5
ω_n/ω_1	1	1.2	1.4	1.7	1.9

where ω_n is the ω when a/b = n.

FIGURE 1. Effect of thickness(1st mode)

FIGURE 2. Effect of transverse shear(1st mode)

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a simple method of calculating the natural frequencies of vibration with considerable accuracy is presented. This method is used to study the effect of transverse shear deformation on vibration of thick laminated composite plates. For this purpose, the influence surface is used from the plate deflection equations based on the assumption that the transverse shear has parabolic variation through the thickness of plate. Comparison is made with the result obtained by using influence surface based on neglecting the transverse shear. Most of the structural members including the floor slabs of bridge, and the floors and the walls of a building are two-dimensional. Most of such elements are elastically supported and have variable cross sections. Obtaining vibration solutions of such elements by any analytical method is impossible. Any numerical method is very much complicated. The method presented herein can solve such problems with relative ease by utilizing the deflection influence surfaces which are used already at the beginning stage of the analysis and design. Since accuracy of the presented method is sensitive only to that of the influence surfaces, it can be concluded that the method presented in this paper is fairly good.

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